

Aseptic mass collection of anthers for increasing efficiency of anther culture in rice breeding

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Anther culture is widely used in rice varietal improvement programs in Korea. The first anther-derived rice cultivar, Hwaseongbyeo, was developed in 1985. Five more have been developed since: Hwacheongbyeo, Hwajinbyeo, Hwaryeongbyeo, Joryeongbyeo, and Hwaseonchalbyeo. These cultivars are being grown on more than 10% of the rice area in Korea.

Recent advances have resulted in increased callus induction and plant regeneration, thus increasing the efficiency of anther culture breeding.

Methods normally used for extracting anthers from rice florets and placing them on media, however, are laborious and time-consuming. They are not appropriate for breeding programs requiring many regenerated plants.

We devised a simple apparatus for aseptic mass collection of anthers. Assembled, it consists of a vacuum source (Fig. 1a) and an aseptic anther-collecting part, made up of a stainless steel cylinder body, 10-ml tube, and extracting glass pipet-tip (Fig. 1b). After being autoclaved, it is used directly in the assembled apparatus.

Rice florets with anthers at the proper stage (uninucleate-binucleate) are clipped and then sucked up by the vacuum with power pressure of 14-20 mm Hg. The collected anthers are immediately transferred from the tube to callus induction medium with a sterilized spatula or forceps in a laminar flow cabinet or clean benches.

We conducted a simple test that showed the anther-planting efficiency of vacuum-collecting to be three times more efficient than that of the conventional method. It took 592 min to plate 5,980 anthers on callus medium with vacuum collection and 601 min to plate 1,743 anthers using the conventional method (see table).

a) The assembled apparatus for aseptic mass collection of anthers consists of a vacuum source and an aseptic anther-collecting part; b) close-up of the anther-collecting part, made of a stainless steel cylinder body, 10-ml tube, and extracting tip.

Comparison of anther-planting efficiency and anther culture response between vacuum collection and the conventional method used in rice anther culture.^a

Anther-collecting method	Anther plating			Anther culture response			
	Anthers plated (no.)	Time elapsed (min)	Time/100 anthers (min)	Callusing		Plant regeneration ^b	
				no.	%	no.	%
Vacuum	5980	592	9.9	1046	17.5	2224	40.5
Conventional	1743	601	34.5	303	17.4	364	20.5

^aMean of 6 replications with 5 japonica genotypes.

^bPlant regeneration (%) = $\frac{\text{No. of plants regenerated}}{\text{No. of anthers plated}} \times 100$.

Frequency of callus induction from anthers was similar for both methods. Plant regeneration rate and absolute number of plantlets were far greater using the vacuum-collecting method (see table). Possible damage and desiccation of immature anthers from suction did not harm anther culturability.

With the vacuum-collecting method,

large amounts of anthers can be gathered quickly and easily, with reduced contamination during collection and plating. This method can enhance efficiency, particularly when sampling large breeding populations. It can also be useful in pollen culture where many isolated pollens are needed for culturing and in *in vitro* selection at haploid level. ■

Polymerase chain reaction amplification of DNA from bacterial pathogens of rice using specific oligonucleotide primers

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The polymerase chain reaction (PCR) is a powerful molecular technique that allows a segment of DNA to be amplified more than a millionfold even when the tem-

plate DNA is present in a very tiny amount. The technique involves cycles of denaturation of duplex template DNA, annealing of two oligonucleotide primers to specific regions in the DNA, and extension of the region flanked by the two primers. This process results in an exponential increase in copy number of the flanked region, permitting specific DNA sequences to be detected with extraordinary sensitivity. Thus PCR can provide a useful diagnostic technique when a high degree of sensitivity is required.

We investigated the possibility of amplifying DNA from bacterial patho-